

Kinray Hub
Indigenous-led R&D

Partnership Design and Ethical research practice framework for Industry R&D

Notes

As the growth of the Kinray Hub network and our BioKulture Dekode business model scalability expands, we aim to collaborate with committed industry and non-profit partners, and will adapt this framework to their practice where applicable, i.e. data collection practices, database management, data usage, data disaggregation praxis, and data interpretation. We aim to utilise this primer as a resource for the responsible integration of biokulture to bio-industry R&D practices.

Background

Genetic material is increasingly being seen as a valuable resource that benefits various societal groups and organisations, such as research scientists, conservation bodies, bio-industry players and medical-pharmaceutical agencies. In an environmental context, insights from DNA analysis of at-source genetic biomaterial serve as a key indicator of ecosystem health, i.e. rare flora and fauna, and soil fertility. Environmental DNA (eDNA) is trace genetic material present in different ecological and micro-environments within one habitat, such as soil, decaying plant and fungal matter, water, and animal faecal matter^{1,2}. Analysed genetic data is typically used to detect the presence of biomarkers for plant and crop health by agricultural development organisations and research scientists, an example of which is microbial symbiosis, through bacterial species profiling and mycorrhizal interactions in the root rhizosphere^{3,4}. eDNA is regarded as a resource of both bioindication for environmental health and inter-species connections, and of-interest organisms for isolating bioactive compounds^{5,6}.

Analysed eDNA data is typically stored electronically in the form of annotated DNA sequences in a genomic database, such as Ensembl^{7,9,14}, with large-scale analysis of environmentally-sourced genomic and extracellular DNA data being performed by registered organisations and institutes such as the Earth Biogenome Project (EBP), the Wellcome Sanger centre, and Oxford Nanopore^{16,17}. Published data can be exclusively managed and owned by the primary researchers based at their respective institution, however partnered organisations with the EBP for example hold a policy of open-access sharing. eDNA data sampled and analysed by non-academic research organisations, for example Hoja Nueva and Basecamp Research, is owned by the organisation at the senior level with quasi-open access for collaborating academic institutes; this is reflected in associated IP. Jurisdiction and legislation surrounding data sampling from lands and biosphere reserves traditional to Indigenous communities, for example in the Peruvian Amazon, can be vague^{9,11}.

In central and south America (LATAM), government bodies hold super-arching control over data sampling laws and the use of genetic data for scientific academic-based research. Data collected by bio-industry players, typically based in Western Europe and North America, also

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possess sole usage and ownership of genetic data sourced from developing countries, displaying a lack of reciprocal data sharing benefits. Genetic research and post-DNA analysis ethical legislation is generally covered by the Nagoya Protocol, however there are a lack of updated clauses to reflect advancements in the field, specifically with post-sequencing manipulation and “Big Data”^{19,20,22}. To remedy this, the creation of local and national-level BioBanks for nature reserves aims to safeguard key resources and facilitate open access data sharing, strengthening research capacity^{11,12,13}.

Across the Amazon basin, there are approximately 380 Indigenous ethnic groups, with traditional lands spanning over 2.4 million square kilometres of territory in four countries. Native biocultural practices have been honed over millennia to simultaneously produce arable cleared land through controlled slash and burn efforts, and species safeguarding by growing co-beneficial crops together, via a deep understanding of soil, and flora and fauna bioindicators²⁶⁻³⁰. In the context of land management and historical rights, established jurisdiction negates the reality of sustained living for Indigenous communities situated on land that is currently part of nature reserves, leading to clashes with externally-set laws on how data can be collected from these protected sites^{26,27,28}. Due to cultural barriers and a legacy of societal ostracism, Indigenous-run collectives and rights groups have limited leverage over influencing data collection laws and practices^{25,32}. Middlemen of government agencies, such as FUNAI (Fundação Nacional dos Povos Indígenas) in Brazil, are also often affected by bribes and corruption from landholders, agricultural players with vested interests in owning and developing previously untouched forest reserves^{25,27}.

Indigenous communities lack concrete and independent data sovereignty laws that protect genetic data sampled from their recognised lands and their original acknowledgement of ownership, including a level of higher decision making regarding data usage^{31,32,33}. This exposes them to extractive and damaging practices, such as “biopiracy” i.e. the theft of natural resources, including genetic material from keystone species vital for the continued self-subsistence of Indigenous groups³⁶⁻³⁹. Bio-prospecting is another term of this practice, the extraction of samples from resource-rich biomes, i.e. Amazonian plants with medicinal and biopharmaceutical compounds, without any recognition or wider benefit to the Indigenous custodians of the region^{40,41,42}.

Currently, no connected umbrella of data protection laws exist at the national level in the capacity to protect against genetic biopiracy and illegal resource extraction, and are notably difficult to enact in underfunded regions bordering the Amazon. However, 2020 marked a turning point in data protection laws and genetic resource protection by the creation of a foundational concept of a DSI (digital sequence information) initiative that recognises the responsible use of DNA in Big and Open data. This was further cemented at the 2024 COP conference in Cali, Colombia^{46,47,64}. There is a pressing need for greater collaboration and multidisciplinary networks between Indigenous communities and local academic institutes, to have a say in relevant research studies and benefit-promoting conservation practices. Pilot studies on data sovereignty practice with Indigenous groups in Alaska, Guatemala and New Zealand showed an improved design of data collection methodology, data management, and analysed data accessibility^{53,58,61}.

Figure 1. Overview of eDNA extraction practices in relation to Indigenous communities. a) Biocultural practices of native agriculture in the Amazon basin, including staple crops and land coverage management. b) eDNA is present in various environments such as soil and water, and can be extracted via sampling methods for oligo purification and further downstream analysis and applications. c) Biopiracy and bioprospecting extract key resources and materials for external use and development, without any reciprocal benefits to immediate local communities or societal infrastructure near biodiversity hotspots in developing countries. d) Enacting a practice framework of data sovereignty awareness enables greater legislative rights of Indigenous groups over genetic bioresources, and strengthens R&D obligations with enacting data transparency, responsible practice, and revenue reciprocity.

There is gradual progress in this area, for example the SEED and +REDD venture firms, that enact a scheme of awarding funding via credits to Indigenous-led organisations and partnered research institutes and collectives to boost local development and sustainability efforts^{53,54,62}. Accreditation for standardised and optimised eDNA analysis workflows by eco-conservation and biotechnology companies aids development and uptake by users willing to pay in using this service. An accredited scheme of bio-credits for genetic data sovereignty could be employed in a similar manner, where the biotechnology company or institute agrees to contribute into a mutually beneficial development fund directed at boosting reliance and scientific training of community members, as a requirement of guaranteed data analysis partnership^{55,57,63}.

Founding a science-based scheme of a local bioeconomy represents a niche area for exploring data sovereignty rights in relation to academic, industrial and community interests⁶⁴⁻⁶⁷. The necessity of resource safeguarding in the face of various socioeconomic and environmental challenges creates a synergistic model of co-benefiting local communities and strengthening R&D practice in the responsible use of genetic data⁶⁷⁻⁷⁰.

Problem statement

There is a current lack of legislative and ethical body guidance on the usage of genetic data by biotechnology R&D companies from Indigenous lands, creating a loophole for potential exploitation and biopiracy. Ethical boards and approved guidelines exist for research performed in academic institutes under supervision, due to a clear and established governing structure, however at present there is less approved comparative legislation for science conducted in the biotechnology industry and at organisation-run labs. For genetic data analysed from tissue samples, cell culture, and microbial engineering, clearer guidelines on scientific practice and data protection exist, but not for ecological and environmental sources of genetic data.

We present a novel legislative research practice framework for responsibly sourcing environmental (eDNA) in resource-rich biomes, intersecting with the lands and traditional ownership of Indigenous groups. We aim to improve data source literacy in industrial R&D practice, and Big Data in a Global South-North axis, sharing and cross-discipline data usage.

Clauses

- 1) Involved Parties agree to abide by local data collection laws and Indigenous-set law frameworks where applicable
- 2) Enact practice of DSI awareness to conduct research adhering to data accessibility laws
- 3) Involved Parties must ensure eDNA analysis and post-sequencing data manipulation fall under ethical genetic data usage regulations
- 4) Indigenous data sovereignty can be defined as an acronym "IDsov" with regards to forming concise and progressive legislation for R&D practice
- 5) Co-operative agreement on participating in foundational bioeconomy development for involved Parties, encompassing capacity development for sustained research practice *in situ*

R&D practice recommendations for Biotechnology industry organisations

- In the context of data sampling and collection, ensure all Parties comply with local government jurisdiction, encompassing both natural reserves ruling and Indigenous community councils and rights boards: that data collection methodologies meet their standards, are not resource-extractive intensive, and cause no ecological damage or pollution.
- Practice awareness of data sovereignty in the form of recognition of key genetic resources, input and output as sequences in a digital medium, and transparency in the translational route of genetic data.

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- Participate in enabling indirect benefits of research for Indigenous communities, avoiding “helicopter research”, i.e. community engagement agreement, participation in roles, guides, basic sampling and transferable skills.
- In the generation of Open data, Big data and accessibility, feedback cycles necessitate an improved medium of database usage, both for industry and academic clients and Indigenous trustees. Ensure accessible database storage and a cyclical feedback chain to local Indigenous-representing bodies based in biodiverse regions of interest.
- Demonstrate clear collaborative networks with established data sovereignty frameworks while incorporating the DACMAR (Disrupt, Adopt, Collaborate, Manage, Adapt, Resources) guideline for successful and responsible biotech R&D performance. See here for full access: <https://qr.codes/Lf0ToO>
- Initiate adherence to updated DSI (Digital Sequence Information) directives and intellectual property of source country bodies in the context of Big Data and the further use of genetic data. Current DSI directives and genetic data use resources can be read here: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-16/cop-16-dec-02-en.pdf> , <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-16/cop-16-dec-03-en.pdf>, sourced from the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).
- Credit opt-in scheme for boosting local biodiversity and bioeconomy efforts, as a method to distinguish R&D work and parent company as being beneficial, and to directly benefit under resourced communities and local *in situ* partners on the ground.

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Appendix

BioKulture Design frameworks (BKD), are for implementing the integration of Indigenous biocultural practices and knowledge into recognised and established bioscience research practice, linked to the context of responsible technical and industrial applications. The diagram below is taken from the publication “Biocultural Design: A new conceptual framework for sustainable development in rural Indigenous and local communities”, illustrating an overview of what constitutes as Biocultural Design and how these practices can lead to innovation. Full article available here: <https://journals.openedition.org/sapiens/1382>

